

INFLUENCE OF THE SERVICE ENVIRONMENT ON THE MATERIAL PROPERTIES OF SHORT- AND ENDLESS-FIBER REINFORCED THERMOPLASTICS

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ABSTRACT

Rising weight and cost requirements in the automotive industry have led to an increasing substitution of metals by short- or endless-fiber reinforced thermoplastics. The use of thermoplastic matrices is necessary to meet the cycle time challenges which arise from large production quantities. The substituted components are often applied in the chassis or motor compartment, which means an exposition to environmental influences, e.g. moisture or thawing salts, during the entire operating lifetime.

Especially polyamide is one of the most used matrix materials and well known for its hygroscopic behaviour. Therefore the moulding material PA66GF30 and organic sheets based on PA6 matrix were investigated in this study. After ageing the materials in water and different thawing salt solutions up to saturation, the static mechanical properties at different saturation-states were determined and an obvious material degradation was observed. A part of the saturated specimens were re-dried to investigate whether the effect is physically or chemically based. In addition, a test rig was developed which allows the spraying of the specimens with the tested mediums during cyclic loading. In this way, the sensitivity of the materials regarding stress corrosion cracking caused by different solutions was determined. In different SN-curves the influence of the service environment on the fatigue strength can be noticed. For the endless-fiber reinforced thermoplastics different material conditioning methods and their influence on the static mechanical properties were investigated. Using a scanning electron microscope, the fracture surfaces of the specimens were investigated in order to detect causes of the material degradation.

Due to the significant degradation of the mechanical properties of polyamide based short- and endless-fiber reinforced plastics an improved knowledge of these mechanisms is essential for a correct component design.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Motivation

Due to the continuous development of technical plastics and polymer composites a current trend in the automotive industry is the substitution of conventional metal components with injection moulded parts. Because of the high design flexibility of this manufacturing process the realization of geometrical optimized structures and the integration of functions is possible. Therefore, a weight

reduction could often be realized. By using short-fiber reinforced plastics (SFRP) the mechanical durability of the material could be further improved. Also the very short production cycle times and good reproducibility are necessary for the large production amounts which are required by the automotive industry. The mechanical properties of SFRPs are sometimes not sufficient for highly loaded applications. Therefore a local reinforcement with endless-glass-fiber (EFRP) could be used. These so called organic sheets are heated up, formed and further reinforced with injected SFRP. This hybrid structures showed a high potential for weight reduction, which was already shown by the fibre reinforced plastics brake pedal, produced by ZF Friedrichshafen AG.

The above described material substitution is often performed for components used in the motor or chassis compartment. Therefore, additional to the mechanical loadings other environmental loads, e.g. moisture, thawing salts or abrasive damage due to stone chip, are superimposed. A widespread thermoplastic matrix for these composite materials is polyamide. This material is well known for its hygroscopy and the associated degradation of the mechanical properties. In this study a polyamide 66 with a short-fiber reinforcement of 30 % w/w (PA66GF30) and an organic sheet with a polyamide 6 matrix (PA6) and an endless glass-fiber reinforcement are used to investigate the influence of moisture and thawing salts on the static and cyclic material properties. The investigation of different thawing salts was chosen, because some manufacturers of the raw material caution the industrial processors against stress corrosion cracking of mechanical loaded polyamide in CaCl_2 solutions.

1.2 Water absorption and material behavior of polyamide

The PA6 and PA66 material show compared to other thermoplastic materials much higher diffusion coefficients D . In [1] PA6 and PA66 plates with 30 % w/w short-glass-fiber reinforcement were exposed in water at different temperatures. The authors showed that the diffusion coefficient is highly dependent on the water temperature. In Fig. 1 the results of this investigation are visualized and displayed the diffusion coefficient D over the water temperature. It can be seen that D is a quadratic function of the water temperature and rises for example for PA66GF30 from 0.2 at 20°C to 90 at 120°C. Also the water content of the specimens at their saturation state changed with the exposition temperature. For the material with polyamide 6 matrix the saturation content of specimens aged at temperatures below 80°C was 5.8 % w/w and above 6 % w/w. The PA66GF30 shows a slightly higher increase of the maximum moisture content. Here, the moisture content at saturation for the specimens below 80°C was only 5 % w/w and rises about 0.5 % w/w for the specimens exposed to water warmer than 80°C.

Figure 1: influence of water temperature on the diffusion coefficient D of PA6GF30 and PA66GF30, [1]

Another important consequence of the moisture absorption of polyamide is the reduction of the glass transition temperature. Polyamide has a semi-crystalline structure and the water molecules are stored inside the amorphous regions [2]. With the usage of a dynamic mechanical thermal analysis (DMTA) a pre-investigation for this work examined the influence of the moisture content on the glass transition temperature T_g . Therefore PA66GF30 specimens were tested at three different states: dry-as moulded, conditioned at 80°C and 50 % relative humidity (r.H.) until a constant mass and saturated in a water bath. The dry-as moulded specimens were re-dried in a vacuum furnace, so the moisture content can be defined as 0 % w/w. The conditioned specimens had a moisture content of 1.6 % w/w and the saturated specimens of 5.9 % w/w. During the DMTA the dynamic storage modulus at different temperatures is measured.

In Fig. 2 the results of the measurements are shown. The abscissa shows the tested temperature range from -40°C to 200°C and the ordinate the normalized storage modulus. There are two characteristic temperatures during the experiment: the so called onset-glass-transition-temperature $T_{g,onset}$ where the storage modulus decreases the first time and the middle-point-glass-transition-temperature $T_{g,middle}$, which is defined through the inflection point of the curve. With regard to the displayed measurements, the influence of the moisture content on the T_g can be seen by the naked eye. The dry material had the $T_{g,middle}$ at 75°C. Due to the conditioning at 80°C and 50 % r.H. the $T_{g,middle}$ decreases to room temperature. Because of the high moisture content of the saturated specimens the $T_{g,middle}$ was measured at -15°C. This strong dependency of the glass transition temperature on the moisture content was also shown in other investigations [3], [4].

Figure 2: dynamic mechanical thermal analysis of PA66GF30 for different conditioning states

If the polyamide is applied in the chassis area, the thawing salts used in winter times by the snow plowing services could influence the material behavior additionally to the effect of the water. Dependent on the prevalent temperature different salts are applied. In regions with moderate temperatures, e.g. Central Europe, sodium chloride (NaCl) is used. Whereas in countries with very low temperatures also calcium-chloride (CaCl₂) is employed [5–7].

The fact that manufacturers of raw materials gave warnings to their customers to avoid mechanical loading on PA6 and PA66 when used in CaCl₂, was the reason for the investigation of this fluid on the mechanical properties in this work [1]. Several other investigations dealt with the stress cracking effects of CaCl₂ and NaCl on polyamide materials and showed that dependent on the fluid-base (e.g. aqueous, methanolic) an influence exists [8], [9].

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Specimens

Two types of specimens are used in this work. For the investigations on the short-fiber reinforced material injection molded specimens made of PA66GF30 are used. The shape of the specimens is in accordance to the *TypIA* defined by the standard DIN EN ISO 527-2 [10]. They have a cross-section of the middle part of 40 mm² and an overall length of 170 mm. The endless-fiber reinforced specimens are made of 6 layers E-glass woven fabrics (with a 0°/90° orientation) with a fiber volume content of 47 % and a polymer matrix made of PA6. The coupon geometry is defined by the standard DIN EN ISO 527-4 *Typ3* [11]. So the specimens had a width of 25 mm and a thickness of 3 mm. All specimens were dried in a vacuum furnace of the type Heraeus Vacutherm VT 6130 M-BL before the conditioning.

2.2 Long-term exposition tests on SFRP

To identify the influence of a long-term exposition in different fluids on the mechanical properties of PA66GF30 the dry-as-moulded specimens were exposed for more than one year. The exposition to fluids and the determination of the fluid absorption of plastics is described in the standard DIN EN ISO 62 [12]. In accordance to this standard the specimens were submerged in the fluids with a temperature of 23°C. The fluids are DI (deionized) water (hereinafter called “H₂O”) and two saturated, aqueous salt solutions made of sodium-chloride (hereinafter called “NaCl”) and calcium-chloride (hereinafter called “CaCl₂”). The change of mass is determined with a precision scale ABT 220-5DM of the manufacturer KERN. At different exposition times a minimum of 6 valid tensile tests were performed on an Instron PL10N hydraulic test machine to determine the changing of the tensile properties due to the fluid exposition. With regard to the standard DIN EN ISO 527-1 [13] the testing speed was 2 mm/min. With the aid of a video extensometer from the manufacturer Messphysik the longitudinal and lateral elongation was measured.

2.3 Combined cyclic mechanical fatigue and environmental loading tests

For exposing the specimens to different fluids during cyclic mechanical loading, a special test rig was developed and built for these investigations. Due to the fact that the whole test rig is made of stainless steel, also the usage of different salt solutions is possible. Additional to the spraying a ventilated heating is applied to simulate drying cycles or increase the ambient temperature during the entire test up to 80°C. In Fig. 3 an assembly drawing and the realization is shown.

A traverse (1) is attached to two shafts (2), which are connected to a baseplate (3). A 40 kN hydraulic cylinder (4) is mounted on this traverse. Equally to the traverse, two crossbeams (5, 6) are fixed to the shafts and the upper one carries a guide bearing (7) to reduce the unguided length of the cylinder shaft, making compression tests possible. The upper clamping tool (8) is attached to the cylinder shaft, while the lower clamping tool (9) is fixed to the load cell (10), which is fixed to the baseplate by a connecting rod (11). The clamping tools are designed for different specimen geometries and thicknesses. Between the load cell and the clamping tool a cooling adapter (12) is connected, to avoid an invalid heating of the load cell during heating cycles. The clamping tools are inside the testing chamber (13) which is attached to the lower crossbeam. The test chamber additionally contains the sprinkle device (14) and the radiator (15).

To prevent a flocculation and evaporation of the test fluid a sealed container with a capacity of 45 liters and an electromechanically agitator is used. As seen in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2 the material properties of conditioned PA66GF30 is highly dependent of the test temperature. To reduce the scatter of the cyclic tests the fluid is controlled to a temperature of 31°C. This temperature was chosen with respect to the self-heating effects of the fluid caused by the circulation and the heat loss of the hydraulic cylinder and the test specimen due to internal friction. A MTS Flextest 100 system was used to control the cyclic loading of the hydraulic cylinder.

Figure 3: combined mechanical fatigue and media exposure stress cracking test rig for mechanical and environmental cyclic loading

2.3 Conditioning and testing of the EFRP

For the EFRP specimens different conditioning methods and their influence on the static tensile properties were investigated. Two test series were conditioned in the climate cabinet WEISS SB22 160 with different climates:

- 50 %r.H. / 80°C until constant mass
- Climatic cycle shown in Table 1

Other specimens were fully immersed in DI water at a temperature of 80°C until saturation. A part of this saturated specimens were re-dried after the exposition in a vacuum furnace.

phase	1	2	3	4	5
duration [min]	60	240	120	240	60
temperature [°C]	+80	+80	-40	-40	+23
relative humidity [%]	80	80	30 (from T < 0°C uncontrolled)		

Table 1: climatic cycle for the conditioning of the EFRP specimens

The static tensile properties were determined on the servo-hydraulic axial testing machine PSA 100 from Schenck. In analogy to the tensile tests of SFRP the testing speed was 2 mm/min. The strain was optically measured by a laser-extensometer of the company Fiedler Optoelektronik.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Exposure tests of SFRP

To identify the influence of a long-term exposition of PA66GF30 to water and different salt solutions the specimens were exposed to these fluids for about one year and at different aging periods static tensile tests were performed. These periods were 3, 10, 50 and more than 370 days. After the exposition until saturation a couple of specimens were re-dried to investigate if the effect of the material degradation is physically – and therefore reversible – or chemically based and not reversible. The results of the tensile tests are shown in Fig. 4, where the bars represent the three different fluids. The exposition time is plotted on the abscissa and the ordinate shows the tensile strength normalized by the initial strength of the dry-as-moulded material. Each bar represents a test series of a minimum of six valid measurements and additionally the triple standard deviation is plotted as error bars.

Figure 4: influence of the exposition time in different fluids on the tensile strength of PA66GF30

After 371 days the material in contact with H₂O is saturated and stores about 6 % w/w water. This leads to a strength degradation of more than 55 % and showed therefore the most adverse effect. The material reached the saturation already after 188 days and therefore this degradation could be expected after this time. Also, the specimens exposed to the salt solutions showed a high reduction of the tensile strength. The coupons in NaCl reduced their tensile strength about 48 % after 385 days and a change of mass of 3.3 % w/w. Exposition to CaCl₂ for 388 days leads to a fluid absorption of 1.7 % w/w and reduces the tensile strength about 38 %.

Regarding the absolute fluid absorption and not the exposition time it can be determined that the degradation effect caused by calcium-chloride is much higher than the effect of H₂O. Using a degradation factor ψ normalized by the absorbed fluid quantity (see equation 1) this consideration could be simplified. The higher the factor ψ is the higher is the reduction of the tensile strength and so the CaCl₂ had a factor ψ of 22. The sodium-chloride had a ψ of 15 and the H₂O of only 9. So the reason for the highest degradation (time considered) of the specimens exposed to H₂O is the much higher diffusion coefficient of water. The re-dried material reached the initially strength again, which leads to the conclusion that the reduction effect is physically based.

$$\psi = \frac{\text{loss of tensile strength}}{\text{absorbed fluid}} \quad (1)$$

3.2 Cyclic mechanical and environmental loading of SFRP

As an implication of the results of the long-term exposition tests two fluids were chosen for the combined fatigue tests: H₂O and CaCl₂. The PA66GF30 material was also tested at the conditioning states dry-as-moulded and conditioned at 50 %r.H. and 80°C until a constant mass. This test setup leads to four different test series for the material. From previous cyclic tests of the material at other test rigs it was known that the scatter of the material lifetime properties is not very excessive. Nevertheless, a first test series with a test frequency $f = 5$ Hz, a load ratio $R = 0.1$ and a stress amplitude $S_{A,norm}$ of approximately 20 % of the ultimate tensile strength (UTS) was performed. As test fluid the DI water was chosen. The results shown in Table 2 verified that the new test rig had a low scatter as well. As a consequence the subsequent fatigue tests were performed after the horizon method, which means that three different load levels with at least three Wöhler tests for each S-N line were tested. The results are fitted to the standard Wöhler function seen in equation 2 [14].

$$\lg N = a - b \cdot S \quad (2)$$

specimen number	normalized stress amplitude $S_{A,norm}$	number of cycles N
01	0,19	282.795
02		343.375
03		279.284
04		242.390
05		179.837
06		252.672

Table 2: results of the scattering test series (conditioned material, $f = 5$ Hz, $R = 0.1$, DI water)

Because of the high temperature dependency of the specimen lifetime on the ambient and therefore the material temperature a reference line without any fluid does not exist. Further tests on an open air test rig showed a large specimen temperature dependency on the load level and therefore such tests are not suitable for a reference curve and not performed. In Fig. 5 the SN- curves for the whole test procedure are shown. The ordinate shows the stress amplitude normalized by the UTS and the number of cycles to failure is shown on the abscissa.

Regarding the influence of the different test fluids, it can be seen that both for the dry-as-moulded and the conditioned material the use of CaCl₂ leads to a minimally decreased lifetime of the material. Although this reducing effect is not particularly striking and with respect to the different loads only existent for the higher load levels, the effect of the initial moisture content on the lifetime can be seen by the offset of the dry (solid line) and the conditioned (dotted line) specimens. The slope of the S-N lines is near the same and the offset is caused by the higher material performance of dry PA66GF30. The specimen moisture content of the conditioned material is comparable to an exposition for about 10 days and already there the static tensile tests showed a material degradation of about 27 % (see Fig. 4).

Considering the high cycle fatigue tests of the dry material the specimens tested in H₂O had a reduced lifetime of about 300.000 cycles to failure. A possible reason could be that the absorption of the dry material leads to internal stresses caused by the swelling of the outer regions of the specimens. This swelling induced a stress concentration in the dry core area, which is superimposed by a second conditioning effect due to the shown reduced T_g with increasing moisture content (see Fig. 2). As a consequence of this stiffness loss a load transfer from the outer layers to the core layers occurs and the inner tensile stresses are additionally increased to the swelling and the cyclic loading. This leads to a premature failure at higher cycles. At higher loads the testing time is due to the test frequency of 5 Hz not large enough to obtain these effects.

Figure 5: S-N lines of PA66GF30 for different conditioning states (dry-as-moulded and conditioned at 50 %r.H. / 80°C until constant mass) and different testing fluids (DI water and aqueous saturated calcium-chloride solution)

3.3 Influence of the material condition on the static tensile properties of EFRP

As described in the chapter *material and methods* the influence of different material conditions on the static tensile properties of the endless glass-fiber reinforced PA6 material was investigated. Therefore a minimum of eight valid tensile tests was performed to examine the material degradation after the conditioning. The results of the tensile tests are shown in Fig. 6. The presentation is similar to the results of the long-term exposition tests of PA66GF30 seen in Fig. 4. The ordinate shows the tensile strength normalized by the UTS of the dry specimens and the error bars show the triple standard deviation of the test series.

Due to the conditioning at a constant climate at 50 %r.H. and 80°C the materials absorbed 0.6 % w/w water and this leads to a decrease of the tensile strength of 13 %. A higher material degradation is caused by the climatic cycle described in Table 1, where the resistance to climate changes is tested. After this conditioning the organic sheet has 80 % of its initial strength left. Because of the high water absorption during the immersion of the specimens in water the loss of tensile strength is the highest in the entire test program. The specimens absorbed 2.6 % w/w water and their strength was reduced to 67 %. The fully saturated specimens were also re-dried in a vacuum furnace. With regard of the scatter of the test these specimens got their initial strength back, so the material damage due to the absorption of water is in analogy to the material behavior of the PA66GF30 reversible and therefore physically based.

3.4 Scanning electron microscopy of EFRP

The fracture surface of the specimens of the conditioning tests were analyzed with the scanning electron microscope SUPRA 40VP from ZEISS. In Fig. 7 the surface for the dry (a) and saturated (b) material is shown at a magnification of 1000. The fiber matrix interface does not seem to be weakened, because in both images the fibers have the same matrix coating. Looking at the pure matrix fracture surfaces it can be seen that the dry material have a more brittle behavior and the conditioned matrix material looks very ductile. This fracture behavior is evidence to the theory that the degradation of the material properties due to water absorption is reversible, because the fiber matrix interface is not affected and the decrease arises from the influence of the water on the matrix properties and the resulting degradation of the load transfer into the fibers.

Figure 6: influence of different material conditionings on the tensile strength of endless-glass-fiber reinforced polyamide 6

Figure 7: fracture of surface of endless-glass-fiber reinforced polyamide 6 for dry (a) and water saturated (b) condition state

4 CONCLUSION

The influence of different fluids on the static and cyclic material properties of PA66GF30 and EFRP with PA6 matrix material was investigated in this work. The long-term exposition of PA66GF30 to water and different salt solutions showed a strong decrease of the static tensile strength. Regarding the test scattering, the combined cyclic mechanical and environmental loading tests of the SFRP with different fluids leads to the result that the strength reduction due to the use of saturated aqueous calcium-chloride solution in comparison to DI water was negligible. The static tensile properties of the organic sheets showed also a high dependency of the conditioning state of the material. Finally both materials get their primary strength back after re-drying. So the damage of the polyamide matrix due to the absorption of water seems reversible.

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